

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF LABORATORY TRAINING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE PHYSICS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the place and role of laboratory training in the development of professional competencies of a future physics teacher. Also, the method of improving the quality of education through the combination of theory and practice is described.*

Keywords: *competence, pedagogical technologies, laboratory, experimental, teaching methodology, didactics of physics, competence, qualification, skill, statistical idea, statistical concept, assessment.*

At the core of the fundamental reforms being carried out in the education system today is the priority task of bringing the quality of education to a new level and ensuring efficiency. Especially, if pedagogy adheres to the principles of consistency in ensuring the compatibility of theory and practice in higher education institutions, connecting it with practice is the main factor in the training of future physics teachers.

It is no secret that the expansion of the scope of information in the education system, the introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies in the physics education system, and the rapid development of science and technology require a competent approach to the educational process (1). The future physics teacher will be able to effectively use complex situations in the course of the physics lesson and be able to get out and make decisions. Through a competent approach, pedagogy serves to improve the methodology of teaching physics in higher education institutions, to bring the training of future physics teachers to a new level, to improve the quality of education, and to solve the priority issue of training competitive personnel.

The times require us to raise our work to a new level aimed at creating modern workplaces for our children, ensuring that they occupy a decent place in life [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

It should be noted that it is possible to train future high-level physics teachers in pedagogical higher education institutions only on the basis of a competent approach to improving the quality of physics teaching and achieving high efficiency. In doing so, the factors of development of competence of future physics teacher will be developed by increasing the quality of education through a competence-based approach to the possibilities of modern achievements of physics teaching methodology.

In complex pedagogical situations, when there is not enough information to come to a clear solution, drawing conclusions and making decisions through a scientific-creative approach is one of the manifestations of the competence-based approach.

The use of advanced ideas and technologies in the educational system, the improvement of the scope of general theoretical questions that make up the content of physics didactics, and the use of statistical ideas and concepts require a special approach to physics teaching methodology.

If there is one side of teaching-learning in education, the rest - active learning and assimilation of acquired knowledge, assessment, creative activity - is the other side.

Our ongoing research shows that competence development begins with the teaching of a physics course in secondary schools. Although physical practicum is often used in general education schools, physical practicum is considered the basis of laboratory training in higher education institutions, and physical knowledge serves as the basis for the development, generalization, deepening, and repetition of experimental skills and skills for its organization and conduct. The development of the future physics teacher's competence, his worldview is achieved by expanding the scope of the specified norms for performing the specified laboratory exercises. Based on the analysis of the literature, the main signs of professional competence were identified.

In order to increase the level of professional training of future teachers, to develop their competence, in addition to deep knowledge of theoretical and practical aspects of educational science, it is necessary to have methodological competence. The current state of the problem of a competence-based approach to the educational process is considered an important factor in the training of future physics teachers and includes the following factors:

1. Identifying the main categories of the competence-based approach and strengthening it through regulatory and legal documents;
2. To create a national Uzbek model of a competence-based approach while preserving national values in general education schools today, to develop a clear and promising plan for training future teachers and to apply it to the educational process;
3. To improve the basics of educational management that ensures the productivity of future physics teachers in the training of future physics teachers;
4. In training mature, competitive physics teachers in the future, to develop their interests, skills in working with technical equipment and devices during laboratory training;
5. Ensuring the priority in the educational system for the professional training of future physics teachers, in addition to the level of learning the harmony of theory and practice, forming the competence of technical knowledge;
6. By characterizing the professional competence of the students of pedagogical institutions in the complex development of competences, relying on the knowledge, skills and abilities of the student in psychological and pedagogical processes in society, he can independently express his attitude to changes in nature and society;
7. To introduce the mechanism of providing additional specializations to future physics teachers.

Competence is an individual quality of a person and implies having certain competencies. Competence is a person's readiness for effective activity in a concrete life situation, knowledge, skills and external resources. Competence is different from knowledge, skills and abilities, and it is manifested in the time of its use or response to the situation. [7,8,9].

In some cases, the student completes individual assignments alone. In the laboratory classes, dividing into small groups (consisting of 3-4 students), each group familiarizes itself with the laboratory development on a separate topic, after getting acquainted with the conditions specified in the instructions for the work to be performed, the procedure for performing the work, they verbally tell the teacher that they have prepared theoretically, and the sequence of performing the work they explain on the basis of questions and answers and, with the permission of the teacher, begin to perform the specified laboratory exercise. In this, a small group works together as a team

to obtain results using a device or equipment. Then the students of the group correct the shortcomings of the completed work, complete their mutual knowledge, and submit the work in the form of a report after mathematical processing of their conclusions. Formation of the competence of a physics teacher is a multifaceted, multiplanned process, and its one-sided evaluation is a complex issue. [7, 8, 9].

Pedagogical research conducted in pedagogical higher educational institutions leads to some difficulties in the fact that the students studying in the field of physics do not have sufficient competence in organizing training sessions from the physical practicum. One of the main reasons for this is the lack of physics teaching hours, including laboratory hours, in secondary schools. Pedagogical studies and observations show that in the groups conducting laboratory training, students with different preparation in physical and mathematical sciences and competence in the development of initial experimental skills show a lack of competence in working with modern measuring devices, low professional competence. In addition, there are always students in groups who are not inclined towards experimental work. Nevertheless, a graduate of the physics-astronomy education department of the pedagogical higher educational institutions should have the competence to conduct laboratory experiments in physics, as well as the skills, abilities to assemble equipment by hand, and the competence to apply it to the educational process.

Current research shows that students neglecting laboratory studies, as well as copying their results using mobile devices, are happening today. The use of modern science and technology achievements by students for their own benefit, among them, the technical possibilities of information exchange through mobile communication tools has reached its peak, the method of not only copying laboratory results from one another, but also "taking" them using mobile communication is developing. Naturally, such methods do not affect the quality of laboratory training.

In the training of the future physics teacher, knowledge of historical stages, formation of pedagogical competence are achieved by in-depth mastering of the scientific basis of physics courses in school and academic lyceums. For this, they should know well how to apply the didactic principle in practice of teaching physics at different levels. However, it cannot be said that pedagogy pays enough attention to this issue in the process of teaching in higher education institutions. Many students find it difficult to apply the competencies they have acquired in pedagogical higher education institutions to teaching school physics courses. The main reason for this is that in the process of teaching physics in general schools, academic lyceums, students show insufficient competence in organizing and conducting physical experiments. The main place in their physical worldview is occupied by dynamic laws, and there is almost no place left for probabilistic statistical laws. The reason for this is the lack of follow-up among the courses of general physics, theoretical physics and physics teaching methodology taught in higher education institutions. The creation of new textbooks by transitioning to improved programs of educational institutions in the general education system leads to an increase in its scientific level.

The above-mentioned ideas remain relevant in the teaching of physical science, the problem of raising the laboratory training in the model curriculum to the level of today's requirements. We believe that if we can develop students' interest in invention and discovery during practical training, it will be a worthy impetus for the rapid development of science and technology, technology and industry of our country, as well as our economy. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

In order for students not to take the laboratory work lightly and to keep the necessary equipment as an eyeball, as well as the level of theoretical preparation is recorded by the teacher, we will increase their responsibility to perform the laboratory work, which will serve to increase the quality of education. Approaching in this way calls students to constant sensitivity, while forming professional competence in them. It should be noted that if the laboratory training is carried out in accordance with the direction and specialty, it would serve to increase the effectiveness of teaching.

If until the end of the 20th century, teaching was largely based on empirical facts, but at the beginning of the 21st century, the opposite, that is, deductive approaches, is required to be the priority. Today, it would be correct to say that the creation of physics educational content is on the agenda, taking into account the latest achievements of science without compromising the educational content and its historicity principle. It is necessary to recognize that the modern physics course reflects the latest achievements of physics in its content. This approach can be considered conceptual, and new developments in the world of methodology can be put on the agenda. We believe that it is necessary to integrate academic subjects, generalize educational information, develop abstract thinking of students and young people, ensure the deductive method of teaching and its priority, and improve the abstract thinking of pupils and students.

As one of the main research methods in experimental science, physics is an object of study in teaching and therefore a co-teaching method. This leads to the fact that the educational experiment takes different forms: demonstration experiment, frontal laboratory work, physical practice. Each of them performs specific didactic tasks. Experimental training is one of the most important elements of competent training of future physics teachers in pedagogical higher educational institutions. Demonstration experiment is conducted together with the explanation of new educational material, and one of its main goals is to visually demonstrate this or that physical phenomenon, to confirm the correctness of the conclusion derived from the studied law or theory. In addition, the purpose of the demonstration experiment is to introduce students to the unique aspects of the experiment as a scientific research method.

Frontal experiments are performed by students during training, usually it is planned for a short period of time. Carrying out frontal experiments develops students' observation, attentiveness, thinking while observing the progress of physical processes, storing information in memory, working with simple tools, performing separate mathematical operations related to measurements, and forming the competence to independently repeat the experiment demonstrated by the teacher. In some cases, frontal experiences are directed to the formation of competences to immediately apply the knowledge gained during the training, to check the correctness of the learned law. Competencies of a relatively complex applied research nature are formed during frontal laboratory work. For example, in the process of performing laboratory work such as determining the density of a substance, measuring the resistance of a conductor, studying the dependence of current in a circuit on resistance and voltage, they collect their devices and their connecting conductors based on the principle and equivalent circuits of temperature, atmospheric pressure, density, resistance, current, voltage, and electrical circuits. Competence of assembling an electric circuit is formed based on the output scheme [10, 11, 12]

The knowledge of the requirements that the physical practicum is a scientific research method is summarized, it ensures a high level of independent work in performing experiments, complex physical devices used in scientific research work (electronic oscillograph, low and high

frequency sound generators, electronic stopwatch, mirror galvanometer, ultra-short wave generators, spectrometers, laser devices, etc.) are formed. In this case, the issue of forming the competence of students to independently plan an educational laboratory experiment and perform sequential actions along with acquiring the necessary skills to conduct experiments that are part of the research elements can be solved by implementing a methodology consisting of the following:

- 1) Clarifying the purpose of experimenting;
- 2) Formulation of hypotheses on which experiments can be based;
- 3) Determination of the necessary conditions for testing hypotheses;
- 4) Making an experiment plan;
- 5) Choosing the necessary equipment, taking measures to replace the missing ones;
- 6) Assembling the experimental device;
- 7) Choosing the method of recording the results of observation and measurement;
- 8) Carrying out the experiment according to the plan in the prescribed manner;
- 9) Mathematical processing of the obtained experimental results;
- 10) Analysis of the obtained results, presentation of graphs and tables, calculation of errors and drawing conclusions;
- 11) Independent performance of tasks related to the topic of laboratory work.

A detailed look at the tasks of the educational experiment and the composition of the actions included in the system of experimental skills. The future physics teacher should be prepared to solve problems in the field of physical experiments during his studies in pedagogical higher educational institutions. A detailed review of the tasks of the educational experiment and the composition of actions included in the system of experimental competences requires from the future physics teacher to be able to solve problems in the field of physical experiments during his studies at pedagogical higher educational institution.

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